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Students' Perception On Difficulties Associated With The Study Of Genetics In Sokoto State University, Sokoto State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examines students' perception on difficulties associated with the study of some of the biological topics and ways to improve the effectiveness of students' learning in biology. As Students perceived the study of genetic in Sokoto State University proves to be difficult. About four research objectives, four research questions and four hypotheses guided the study. This study employed survey research design. The population of the study consists of 459 Biological Science and Biology Education Students in the study area. Purposive sampling technique was used to select 210 Biology students. For these purposes, a self-administered questionnaire including four open-ended questions was employed to collect the data. The instruments was validated and subjected to corrections. While the reliability index was estimated using Cronbalch Alpha statistics and it produced an average index of 0.86. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze quantitative data using frequencies and percentages in table. This was used to determine and answers in the research questions. The results found that Students perceived the study of genetic in Sokoto State University to be difficult. The finding also reveals that Students perceived the teaching method used in learning genetics concept in Sokoto State University to be less effective. Also, the factors associated with the difficulties in the teaching and learning of genetics concept in Sokoto State University include inappropriate teaching methods, cultural beliefs and practices, lecturers' competency, abstractness of Genetics and genetics complexity, vocabulary and terminology. Therefore, the study recommends that Students should be encouraged to change their perception of Genetics as is not as difficult as it seems. Also, modern method of teaching like teaching with analogy, scientific argumentation instructional method, use of Computer Assisted Learning and problem based learning method should be adopted. It was suggested that similar study should be carried out in other areas in the state and beyond, so as to compare if there will be any similarities in their findings.

Keywords: Biology Difficulties, Genetics, Perception, Students.

INTRODUCTION

Biology is seen as a natural science subject whose scope ranges from microscopic organism to the biosphere that is ecosystem. Biology is described as the scientific study of life. It is a discipline with different branches ranging from genetics evolution, ecology and so on and is therefore recognized as broad (Ramlingam, 2021). Genetics as an aspect of Biology is concerned with the study of nature and

mechanism of heredity or the study of genes (Singh, 2019). Accordingly, Anderson, Fisher and Norman (2012) have defined genetics as the transfer of characteristics of an organism from the parents to the offspring.

Genetics is an important course at both secondary and tertiary levels of education in Nigeria. The inclusion of genetic in secondary and tertiary institutions biology curriculum shows the importance of the course to the society (Singh, 2019). However, with the great importance that the course offers student academic performance continues to dwindle for many years now in this discipline.

Genetics have been perceived to be difficult for some students and teachers (Knippels, Waarlo, & Boersma, 2015). Difficulties could be due to the misconceptions students and teachers have about various subtopics in genetics as revealed in the findings of several studies (Altunoglu and Seker, 2015; Shaw et al., 2018; Yates & Marek, 2013).

Knippels, Waarlo, & Boersma, (2015), determined some difficulties which should be effective in genetic education: the domain-specific terminology, the cytological processes and the abstract nature of the genetics concepts. In addition to the nature of topic, some cognitive factors like reasoning ability and learning orientation have effect on learning of abstract and complex topics. Abimbola (2018) investigated the Biology content areas that Biology teachers perceived as important but difficult for them to teach and reasons they gave for their perceptions. Some teachers' see some Biology concepts as being too complex for students understanding; most especially genetics concepts (Abimbola, 2018). Furthermore, Soyibo (2020) also researched into the teaching of genetics. In his work on conceptual and instructional difficulties in 'O' level genetics, the researcher reports that the teaching of genetics has been neglected in most secondary schools in Nigeria.

This problem is not limited to Nigeria alone, Michael (2019), stated that, despite the national efforts of the United States to improve Science Education. Students of United States continue to lag behind their peers as high rate of under-performance in genetics. This showed that the poor performance of students in tertiary institution in genetic is endemic. He also discovered that teaching and learning of genetics has become a tough task which teachers of biology tend to avoid and students have found it to be a monster ought to be avoided rather than discipline to be engaged.

In addition, research findings showed a poor understanding of the processes by which genetics information is transferred from teacher to students; a lack of basic knowledge about the structure involved (e.g. gene, chromosomes, cell) and widespread uncertainty and confusion among Nigerian students of various levels especially tertiary institution and among the population in general (Akinnubi, Oketayo, Akinwande, & Ifedayo, 2022).

The nonchalant attitude of all the parties concerned with the teaching and learning of genetics particularly, the teachers could be attributed to the nature and type of genetic questions answered by students from time to time (Soyibo, 2016). Also, he stresses the need for Biology teachers to develop positive attitude towards the teaching of genetics concepts because these concepts are important to everyday life. Other attributable reasons for low performances of students in genetics concepts include lack of instructional materials, abstractness, complexity, sophistication of concept, short allocation of hours of practical, insufficient teaching experience, poor background of student, lack of Biology lecturers' interest, lack of students' interest, lack of training and retraining programs for lecturers, lack of motivation to lecturers, inadequate text books for genetics, inadequate fund for maintenance of laboratory, genetics materials, lack of practical in genetics, problem of handling large classroom, lack of good text books from local authors, variation of genetics concepts in various textbooks, and insufficient postgraduate courses in genetics.

Furthermore, according to Nzelum (2020), different reasons are responsible for students' poor performance, some of which are due to the abstractness of certain aspects of biology, lack of understanding on the students' part of certain biological concept and terminologies. As a result of failure experienced in the genetics aspects of biology students tend to avoid genetics and teacher also attempt to ignore the topic citing various excuses. It is against this background that this study seeks to examine students' perception on difficulties associated with the study of genetics in Sokoto State University, Sokoto.

Statement of Problems

Several biological topics were identified by their level of difficulty in terms of instruction by teachers, as well as the difficulty which student have in learning argued that genetic is generally described by most students as the most difficult aspect of biology in higher institutions. Literatures on science education has indicated several major reasons as being the cause of the difficulty associated with the learning genetics in tertiary institutions. These different problems are not isolated, but in a way related to one another and can reinforce the difficulties students' experience. Students face problems in the abstract and complex nature of science knowledge, their own ingrained misconceptions, and the large amount of context. However, students' ability to deal with formal concepts in a meaningful manner is connected with their level of intellectual and cognitive development

The issue of poor performance at secondary school in Biology concept has been of great concern to many researchers as reported by Olatoye (2023). Identified the difficulty of the concepts of genetics and failure to use appropriate teaching method such as problem-based learning and use of analogy as the cause of students' poor performance in biology concepts including genetics. One effective way to deal with this problem is for the teacher to provide a bridge between the unfamiliar concepts and the knowledge which the student possesses. This bridge can be the use of analogy which allows abstract concepts to be easily assimilated with the students' prior knowledge thus enabling them to develop an understanding of the concept.

Undoubtedly, many would acknowledge that genetics is an important subject to learn in these days and age where its applications are numerous and even the cause of many debates. However, due to the nature of the subject matter and possibly, the way it is being taught, the understanding of genetics by many students is thought to be very poor. Studies have indicated that performance of students in some difficult concepts in Biology still remain poor. Not much attempt seems to have been made towards finding out how students perceived these difficulties in Sokoto metropolis in particular and Nigeria at large. It was purely in an attempt to bridge the gap that this study was carried out.

More so, many factors may account for students' poor performance some difficult concepts in Biology, it is evident that most students have difficulties in learning some concepts. In addition to the nature of topic, some cognitive factors like attitude and learning orientation have effect on learning of abstract and complex concepts. This paper is being carried out for the purpose of redressing this trend in the study area. It is in line with this that this study seeks to examine students' perception on difficulties associated with the study of genetics in Sokoto State University.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine students' perception on difficulties associated with the study of genetics in Sokoto State University, Sokoto. The specific objectives include:

1. To find out how students perceive the study of genetics in Sokoto State University.
2. To determine the students' perception on teaching method used in learning genetics concept in Sokoto State University?
3. To identify the factors associated with the difficulties in the teaching and learning of genetics concept in Sokoto State University.

Research Questions

To achieve the objectives of this research, the following research questions were used to guide the study:

1. How do students perceive the study of genetic in Sokoto State University?
2. What are students' perception on teaching method used in learning genetics concept in Sokoto State University?
3. What are the factors associated with the difficulties in the teaching and learning of genetics concept in Sokoto State University?

Research Hypotheses

This research is guided by the following:

H01: There is no significance differences in how students perceive the study of genetic in Sokoto State University?

H02: There is no significance differences in students' perception on teaching method used in learning genetics concept in Sokoto State University?

H03: There is no significance differences in the factors associated with the difficulties in the teaching and learning of genetics concept in Sokoto State University?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive survey research design.. The choice of the design is based on the fact that it entails the research er collecting, analyzing and reporting the outcome as it exists in the field without manipulation of variables.

Population of the Research

The population of the study consists of all the Biology and Biology Education Students of 200 and 300 in the study area comprising of 206 and 253 respectively making a total of 459 students.

Sample and Sampling Technique

Using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table of determining sample size, a sample size of 210 students was selected from the total population of 459 Biology students. Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting Biology students for this research. According to Maxwell (2002), purposive sampling is used in selecting a particular person(s) deliberately so as to supply important information. The choice for purposive sampling technique in selecting the respondents hinges on efficient prediction of result and since the study matter concerns the Biology students. The sample size of the students is shown in the table 1

Table 1:- Sample size of levels and students

S/N	Level	Biology Students	EducationBiology Students	Total
1.	200	50	45	95
2.	300	60	55	115
	Total	110	100	210

Sources: Research work, 2025

Instrumentation

A structured questionnaire was used in collecting the data for this research. The questionnaire will be titled Difficulties Associated in Learning Genetics Questionnaire (DALGQ) comprising of 20 items dwelling on the subject matter. The questionnaire was divided into four sections A, B, C and D. Section A comprised of the demographic data of the respondents, section B cover questions relating to how students' perceived the study of genetics, section C is question on teaching methods and performance in genetics, while section D capture questions on factors associated with the difficulties in the study of genetics and students' academic performance. A four point Likert Scale questionnaire guide of agreed (A), strongly agree (SA), disagreed (D) and strongly disagree (SD) was used as the response format for the respondents.

Validation of the Instrument

The instrument was subjected for content validity through some two experts (2) from Faculty of Sciences, Sokoto State University, Sokoto. This was done for the instrument to measure what it was se to t measure. The correction made was effected before administering to the respondents.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was determined using pilot test involving twenty (20) respondents from the target population who are also part of the population but not part of the selected sample for the study. It involves administering the same questionnaire to different subjects who are not part of the study sample. The reliability index of the instrument was measured using Cronbach Alpha and a reliability coefficient score of 0.86 was determined. This moderately high coefficient values indicate that the instrument is reliable and therefore was adjudged high enough for the study.

Method for Data Collection

The researcher administered the questionnaire to the respondents. However, permission will be sought from the school authority through a letter of introduction from the researcher’s institution. The respondents would be given adequate time to complete the questionnaire and was personally retrieved by the researcher.

Method of Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics was used to analyze quantitative data using frequencies and percentages in answering the research questions

RESULTS

Table 2: Students’ Perception of Genetics

S/N	Items	AGREED %		DISAGREED %	
1.	Students are frightened when it comes to the study of Genetics	150	(75%)	50	(25%)
2.	Students perceived genetics concepts to be difficult	135	(68%)	65	(32%)
3.	Students understand the concepts of Genetics quite easily	45	(22%)	155	(78%)
4.	Learning Genetics is an enjoyable experience	105	(52%)	95	(48%)
5.	Genetics is tedious to study	140	(70%)	60	(30%)
6.	Genetics is not fun to study	95	(48%)	105	(52%)
7.	Genetics is a very important aspect of the Biology curriculum	160	(80%)	40	(20%)

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 2 presents the distribution of students’ perception of genetics. From the table, it shows that 75% of the respondents agree that sstudents are frightened when it comes to the study of Genetics while 25% of them disagree. 68% of them agree that students perceived genetics concepts to be difficult while 32% of them disagree. 22% of them agree that sstudents understand the concepts of Genetics quite easily while 78% of them disagree. 52% of them agree that learning Genetics is an enjoyable experience while 48% of them disagree. 70% of them agree that Genetics is tedious to study while 30% of them disagree. 48% of them agree that Genetics is not fun to study while 52% of them disagree. 80% of them agree that Genetics is a very important aspect of the Biology curriculum while 20% of them disagree. Base on the responses on students’ perception of genetics in the study area, it can be observed from the high percentage of agreement with the various items that the students perceived Genetics to be a tough concept as they find it difficult to understand.

Table 3: Students Perception on Teaching Methods Used in Learning Genetic Concept

S/N	Items	ADREED %		DISAGREED %	
1	Inappropriate teaching methods negatively affect students learning of genetics concepts	160	(80%)	40	(20%)
2	Students' cultural beliefs and practices is associated with poor understanding of genetics concept	155	(78%)	45	(22%)
3	Lecturers' competency of subject matter is link with student learning of genetics concept	150	(75%)	50	(25%)
4	Abstractness of Genetics is a major factor towards genetics learning	164	(82%)	36	(18%)
5	Genetics complexity, vocabulary and terminology is a major cause of poor understanding of genetics concepts	180	(90%)	20	(10%)

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 3 presents the distribution of students' perception on teaching methods used in learning genetic concept. From the table, it shows that 75% of the respondents agree that teaching with analogy will increase students understanding of genetics while 25% of them disagree. 68% of them agree that scientific argumentation instructional method will better improve students understanding of genetic concepts while 32% of them disagree. 78% of them agree that use of Computer Assisted Learning will improve student's learning in genetics concept while 22% of them disagree. 70% of them agree that traditional lecture method makes teaching of genetics more difficult while 30% of them disagree. 78% of them agree that problem based learning method increases students understanding of genetics while 22% of them disagree. Base on the responses on students' perception on teaching methods used in learning genetic concept in the study area, it can be observed from the high percentage of agreement with the various items that the methodology used in teaching Genetics contribute greatly towards student learning of the concept as such the modern method of teaching the concept is more effective.

Table 4: Factors Associated With the Difficulties in the Teaching and Learning of Genetics Concept

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S/N	Items	ADREED	%	DISAGREED	%
1	Inappropriate teaching methods negatively affect students learning of genetics concepts	160	(80%)	40	(20%)
2	Students' cultural beliefs and practices is associated with poor understanding of genetics concept	155	(78%)	45	(22%)
3	Lecturers' competency of subject matter is link with student learning of genetics concept	150	(75%)	50	(25%)
4	Abstractness of Genetics is a major factor towards genetics learning	164	(82%)	36	(18%)
5	Genetics complexity, vocabulary and terminology is a major cause of poor understanding of genetics concepts	180	(90%)	20	(10%)

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 4 presents the distribution of factors associated with the difficulties in the teaching and learning of genetics concept. From the table, it shows that 80% of the respondents agree that inappropriate teaching methods negatively affect students learning of genetics concepts while 20% of them disagree. 78% of them agree that students' cultural beliefs and practices is associated with poor understanding of genetics concept while 22% of them disagree. 75% of them agree that lecturers' competency of subject matter is link with student learning of genetics concept while 25% of them disagree. 82% of them agree that abstractness of Genetics is a major factor towards genetics learning while 18% of them disagree. 90% of them agree that Genetics complexity, vocabulary and terminology is a major cause of poor understanding of genetics concepts while 10% of them disagree. Base on the responses on students' perception on factors associated with the difficulties in the teaching and learning of genetics concept in the study area, it can be observed from the high percentage of agreement with the various items that the various factors actually contribute to the teaching and learning of Genetics as such students fail to comprehend the concept as taught.

Summary of Findings

Base on the result , it was found that:

1. Students perceived the study of genetic in Sokoto State University to be difficult
2. Students perceived the teaching method used in learning genetics concept in Sokoto State University to be less effective
3. The factors associated with the difficulties in the teaching and learning of genetics concept in Sokoto State University include inappropriate teaching methods, cultural beliefs and practices, lecturers' competency, abstractness of Genetics and genetics complexity, vocabulary and terminology

DISCUSSION

From the descriptive analysis, Students perception of genetics learning was found that Students are frightened when it comes to the study of Genetics, Students perceived genetics concepts to be difficult, Students do not understand the concepts of Genetics quite easily, Learning Genetics is an enjoyable experience despite its difficulty in learning, Genetics is tedious to study, Genetics is fun to study despite being a difficult concept to study and Genetics is a very important aspect of the Biology curriculum. Therefore, based on the research question, how does students perceived the study of genetic in Sokoto State University? It can be observed that students perceived the study of Genetic in Sokoto State University to be a difficult concept. This might be as a result of one or more reasons which can be linked to barriers to effective teaching and learning.

This is in agreement with the finding of Knippels et al., (2015) who assert that Genetics is perceived difficult by students and even teachers. One of the reasons for difficulty of genetics concepts is unfamiliarity of students with the definitions of the genetics related terms because terms look and sound very similar (Bahar et al, 2019). This finding also agrees with Lewis and Kattmann (2018) who also stated that genetics is considered to be one of the most difficult concepts in biology and the mechanisms are hard to understand because it is difficult to make the ideas to be tangible without the help of special instruments. The study further revealed that students come to the classroom with their own conceptions of genetics from their own experience and observations.

From the descriptive analysis of the Students perception on Teaching Methods used in genetic learning, it was found that Teaching with analogy will increase students understanding of genetics, Scientific argumentation instructional method will better improve students understanding of genetic concepts, Use of Computer Assisted Learning will improve student's learning in genetics concept, Traditional lecture method makes teaching of genetics more difficult and Problem based learning method increases students understanding of genetics. This agrees with the study of Tuomas and Anna (2018) that carried out an investigation on the methods of teaching genetics. It was found that the study suggests that teacher experience on the methodology in teaching genetics correlates strongly with how students perceive what the core content of genetics is.

Most biology teachers prefer to teach in a traditional lecture method as it was found to be easier and faster to cover the syllabus on time but this way of teaching hindered the students understanding of Genetics (John et al., 2019). Therefore, it has been considered that the use of motivational active learning like Problem based learning and scientific argumentation) will make the students more alert, motivated and highly participative, being interested in the subject and thus enhancing their performance (Rodríguez et al., 2018). As such, students perceived these teaching methods to be more efficient and effective in the study of genetic concepts.

From the descriptive analysis of Factors associated with the difficulties in the teaching and learning of genetics, it was found that Inappropriate teaching methods negatively affect students learning of genetics concepts, Students' cultural beliefs and practices is associated with poor understanding of genetics concept, Lecturers' competency of subject matter is link with student learning of genetics concept, Abstractness of Genetics is a major factor towards genetics learning and Genetics complexity, vocabulary and terminology is a major cause of poor understanding of genetics concepts. This is accordance with the finding of Knippels et al. (2015) which revealed some major difficulties experienced by students which are (a) the domain-specific vocabulary and terminology, (b) the mathematical content of Mendelian genetics tasks, (c) the cytological processes, and (d) the abstract and complex nature of genetics. This is also in agreement with the study of Duncan and Reiser (2017) who opined that genetics is difficult for students to learn because of the invisibility and inaccessibility of genetic phenomena.

CONCLUSION

Genetics is a basic topic in biology however it is perceived difficult by students and even teachers. These difficulties arise as a result of the domain-specific terminology, the cytological processes and the abstract nature of the genetics concepts. In addition to the nature of topic, some cognitive factors like reasoning ability and learning orientation have effect on learning of abstract and complex topics like Genetics.

Based on the findings of the results, it was concluded that students perceived the study of Genetic in Sokoto State University to be difficult. This difficulty can be attributed to various reasons which can be linked to barriers to effective teaching and learning of the topic which include teaching methodology, cultural beliefs and practices, lecturers' competency of subject matter, abstractness of Genetics as well as Genetics complexity,

vocabulary and terminology. All these and many more may have impaired their understanding and resulted in the difficulties they encounter in learning genetics.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Base on the findings, this paper recommended that for a better understanding of the concept,

1. Students should be encouraged to change their perception of Genetics as is not as difficult as it seems.
2. Modern method of teaching like teaching with analogy, scientific argumentation instructional method, use of Computer Assisted Learning and problem based learning method should be adopted. There is need to make the subject content more contemporary, meaningful and interesting for the students, reflecting the current developments in the field and relating teaching/learning process with daily life issues. However, biology instruction should be supported by qualified textbooks, instructional materials, hands-on, mind-on sessions and observations as well as experiments that actively engage students in learning processes.
3. The factors associated with learning difficulties should looked into and addressed while teaching/learning the topic.

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